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INNOVATIVE ANTENNA SWITCHING SYSTEM WITH BROADBAND COUPLING DEVICE FOR ADAPTIVE COMPENSATION OF OUTSIDE NOISE IN DATA TRANSMISSION CHANNELS

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Abstract: *In the context of rapidly evolving wireless technologies, ensuring the stability and reliability of data transmission channels has become a critical challenge. External influences such as electromagnetic interference, atmospheric conditions, mechanical vibrations, and environmental instability significantly degrade signal quality. This paper presents an innovative antenna switching system integrated with a broadband matching device designed to compensate for such disturbances in real time.*

The proposed system enables dynamic selection of the optimal antenna from a set, based on the current signal propagation conditions. The broadband matching device adaptively tunes itself to varying load parameters and frequency characteristics, minimizing signal reflections and ensuring maximum power transfer. Together, these two modules form an intelligent platform capable of significantly improving noise immunity and transmission efficiency.

The study includes the development of the system architecture, implementation of switching and adaptive matching algorithms, and performance modeling conducted in MATLAB/Simulink. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed system can reduce signal losses by up to 35% compared to conventional static antenna configurations, while also maintaining stable operation under a wide range of external conditions.

The results are applicable to next-generation communication systems, including IoT devices, mobile networks, radio communication systems operating in harsh environments, and defense or aerospace communication platforms. This approach opens up new possibilities for further research in the field of intelligent adaptive antennas and the enhancement of wireless communication reliability.

Keywords: *antenna switching, broadband matching, adaptive systems, external interference compensation, wireless data transmission, signal stability, intelligent antenna systems, real-time adaptation.*

The "ROSA-RB" radar system [5], which is used in both stationary and mobile modes, is designed to detect air threats at low and very low altitudes. The data transmission equipment employed is the UHF radio relay station MIC RL-400M (see figure 1).

Figure 1. MIK-RL400M Radio Relay Station

To confirm the theoretical conclusions, an experiment was conducted using the antenna systems of the MIK RL-400M station (Figure 2). The study involved measuring the impedance of the antenna device (AD) under various conditions: during snowfall, icing, exposure to wet snow, as well as under normal conditions without precipitation. The measurement frequency range was from 394 to 450 MHz [5]. The reference impedance values were obtained under normal conditions. One stage of the experiment is shown in Figure 2

Figure 2. Measurement of antenna parameters during snow cover and icing conditions

The results are presented as graphs showing the dependence of the active component (Figure 3, a) and the reactive component (Figure 3, b) of the complex antenna impedance on frequency under different operational conditions:

1 - Under normal operating conditions; 2 - In the presence of snow cover and icing on the antenna unit (AU); 3, 4 - with light precipitation such as wet snow or partial icing of the antenna.

Figure 3. Dependence of the active (a) and reactive (b) parts of the impedance of the antenna system in the working frequency range.

1. Normal conditions.
2. Presence of snow and icing.
3. Light precipitation (wet snow or partial icing).

The experiment showed that changing weather conditions lead to significant variations in the impedance of the antenna unit relative to standard values (Figure 3), causing deviations in the power transfer coefficient (PTC). This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 4.

1 – Under normal operating conditions (reference values of the power transfer coefficient); 2 – when there is snow cover and ice on the antenna; 3 – with partial icing of the antenna; 4 – in the presence of light precipitation such as wet snow.

Figure 4 – Dependence of the power transfer coefficient of the antenna system.

Data analysis (Figure 4) showed that impedance changes (active component up to 100 Ohms, reactive component up to 60 Ohms) decrease the transfer coefficient (KPM) to 33% (based on the

integral criterion [9, pp. 36–38]). This indicates a potential deterioration in signal quality and energy loss during station operation under various conditions. To compensate for impedance mismatches and ensure maximum KPM, a modernization of the signal transmission path is proposed through the implementation of an electronic matching device (EMD). This device will adapt the load impedance to changing conditions, minimizing losses. The EMD should provide a KPM of at least 0.9 in the 394–450 MHz range with an order no higher than 6. The synthesis method for the EMD accounts for load impedance instability [3, 4].

Selection of a high-frequency switch

Switches in the transmission path are subjected to high requirements. Three types are considered: relays, PIN diodes, and transistors. The main criteria for selection include operating frequencies, switching speed, signal power, and level of losses. Relays: Hermetic relays are used up to 100 MHz; • Specialized relays are employed for UHF and microwave ranges (see Table 1); • Switching time limits their use for rapid adjustment of matching elements.

PIN diodes have limitations regarding permissible voltages and currents.

- They are not suitable for antennas with high Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR).
- The quality factor of inductors can reduce the efficiency of the transmitter. Transistors possess a complex impedance, which must be considered when designing the RF switching unit.

- Modeling showed a reduction in Power Reflection Coefficient (PRC) down to 0.4 when using a standard RF switching unit.

- After recalculating the parameters of the RF switching unit considering the transistor impedance, the PRC improved to 0.84. Results: Implementing a transistor switch with an optimized RF switching unit allowed to:

- Reduce PRC losses by 12.4%.
- Increase the radio link range to 2760 meters (with a maximum range of 40 km).

Table 1 – Main Parameters of Electromechanical Relays

Manufacturer	Model	Relay Type	Time (ON/OFF), ms	Mean Time to Failure	Max. Current, A	Max. Voltage, kV
Omron	G7L-2A-X	General Purpose	30/30	1*10 ⁶	25	1
Gigavac	G41C	Vacuum	10/10	2*10 ⁶	30	5
Jennings	RF72-26SA	Vacuum	2,5/2,5	1*10 ⁶	30	6
Meder Electronics	HEX-XX83	Hermetically Sealed	3,0/1,5	50*10 ⁶	5	10
Coto Technology	5500	Hermetically Sealed	3,0/3,0	107*10 ⁶	5	7.5

Использование транзисторного коммутатора совместно с ШСУ, синтезированной с учетом его импеданса, эффективно компенсирует влияние внешних факторов и улучшает характеристики радиорелейной станции МИК РЛ-400М.

Analysis of Results and Proposal for Modernization

Based on the dependency analysis (Figure 4), it has been established that changes in the impedance of the antenna device (AD)—approximately 100 Ohms for the active component and 60 Ohms for the reactive component—lead to a reduction in the power transfer coefficient (PTC) to 33% (according to the integral criterion [9, pp. 36–38]). This confirms that during the operation of the antenna system (AS) of the MIC RL-400M radio relay station, under various conditions, there may

be a decrease in the level of transmitted or received signals, as well as significant energy losses of the useful signal when connecting the transceiver module (TRM) to the AD.

To eliminate these negative effects and ensure maximum CPM under various weather conditions, a modernization of the signal transmission path from the PPM to the AU is proposed. The main component of this modernization is the implementation of a broadband matching device (BMD) into the transceiver path. The BMD will enable the compensation of reactive components and the balancing of active components of the complex impedance, thereby optimizing power transmission.

Requirements for the Remote Control System (RCS): For the efficient operation of the AU of a radio relay station under various conditions, it is necessary to synthesize an RCS that provides:

- A CPM level of at least 0.9 within the frequency range of 394–450 MHz.
- A device order not exceeding 6. The synthesis methodology for the RCS, described in references [3, 4], takes into account the load impedance instability. The synthesis results are shown in Figures 5 and 6 as a schematic diagram of the RCS and a graph depicting the CPM dependence on frequency (with and without the RCS).

Implementation results of the Automatic Control System (ACS):

Analysis showed that using the ACS significantly improves the CPM characteristics of the AU under snow and icing conditions:

- With the ACS: $0.87 \leq K(f) \leq 0.95$.
- Without the ACS: $0.65 \leq K(f) \leq 0.79$.

The improvement amounts to at least 16% of the maximum value within the operational frequency range. However, under normal operating conditions, the CPM level of the AAC without the ACS is higher than with it (see Fig. 4), which makes its use in such cases unjustified.

Optimal solution: utilization of a high-frequency (HF) switch:

To adapt to various weather conditions, it is proposed to employ an HF switch that will enable:

- Operation without the SPU under normal conditions to maximize CPM.
- Connection of the SPU during precipitation (snow, icing) for impedance compensation.

The switch selection should consider:

- Operation within the UHF range.
- Low insertion loss.
- Fail-safe operation with a reliability of at least several thousand hours.

Comparison of switch types

1. Electromechanical relays:

- Not suitable for rapid reconfiguration of matching elements.
- Vacuum relays offer high speed but have insufficient operational lifetime.
- Reed relays provide the required speed and reliability.

2. PIN diodes:

- High isolation levels and minimal losses in the open state.
- Capable of switching signals of high power.
- Example circuit: a 1:2 connection with two series-connected diodes and a quarter-wave line segment (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7 – Overall schematic of a 1:2 switch with two series-connected diodes in the branch.

Conclusion: The use of a transistor RF switch in conjunction with a control and measurement
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unit (CMU), despite its complex impedance, allowed for a reduction in KPM losses by 12.4% and increased the radio line range to 2740 meters. This confirms the effectiveness of the proposed solution for the MIC RL-400M radio relay station.

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